

City of
Doncaster
Council

NIHR | Health Determinants
Research Collaboration
Doncaster

HDRC Blogpost by Verity Place and Ava Hodson

Hi, I'm Verity, and I'm a Graduate Management Trainee currently based in the Healthy Places Team within Public Health. Over the past six months, I have been working on the development of a Road Safety Strategy alongside the Road Safety Team and the Transportation Team.

To ensure our strategy was evidence-based and well-informed, we submitted a request to Doncaster council's unique [HDRC programme](#). HDRC stands for Health Determinants Research Collaboration and is a programme available to local authorities funded by the NIHR; it aims to embed research practice into local authority decision-making and policy-formation to ensure that practitioners are equipped to make evidence-based decisions.

Because of this, I was introduced to Dr Ava Hodson, an embedded researcher from the University of Sheffield, who supported me throughout the process of conducting a systematic review of existing evidence and literature related to road safety.

Through Ava's mentorship and skills-sharing, I learnt the full technical and academic process of conducting a literature review, including developing search strategies, writing a protocol, and carrying out thematic analysis. We shared the workload and collaborated at each stage, which made the experience both efficient and enjoyable. Overall, working on this review was incredibly valuable.

Together, we produced a report, with findings and recommendations that will be integrated into the final Road Safety Strategy. We've already started disseminating our findings too; it has been shared with staff across the council to help inform a range of ongoing and future work that will ensure safer roads for the residents and visitors of Doncaster. It also formed a large discussion point in our recent meeting with stakeholders and collaborators from fire, police, National Highways and charities such as [Brake!](#) and [HOPE South Yorkshire](#). With some tweaks and refinements, Ava is planning for it to be written into a journal publication – watch this space! You can read our report for yourself [here](#).

The collaborative approach that the HDRC upholds meant that completing this piece of research was both interesting and informative. Furthermore, Ava's thorough, clear and accessible support has equipped me with research skills that I can carry forward into my next placement and future roles. Writing the report was genuinely enjoyable and insightful, but mostly satisfying to see it finished at the end and informing our public health work at the council!